

Relationship between Parenting Style with Academic Motivation, Anxiety and Academic Performance among adolescents

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Abstract

We investigated the influences of motivation, goal orientation, and self-efficacy on the relationships between parenting styles and academic performance, as well as the mediating impacts of these factors. A total of one hundred forty-eight high school students took part in the event, with 58 boys and 90 females participating. Students were asked to fill out a questionnaire called the Parenting Style/Parental Involvement Questionnaire in order to gauge their opinions regarding the parenting styles of their parents. The pupils' levels of motivation were evaluated using the Intrinsic-Extrinsic Orientation Scale. Goal orientation and academic self-efficacy were both evaluated by the Patterns of Adapted Learning Survey, which was administered to participants. It was discovered that adolescents who stated that their parents had a parenting style that was more authoritative exhibited a higher level of intrinsic drive in their academic efforts. There is a discussion on the potential future implications for intervention and study. While academics frequently use the terms parenting styles and parenting practices interchangeably, it is important to note that there is a distinction between the two notions.

KEY WORDS: PARENTING STYLE, ACADEMIC MOTIVATION, ADOLESCENTS

According to Baumrind (1967, 1973) and Maccoby and Martin (1983), the following is a list of the four different types of parenting styles and the traits that are typically associated with each of them:

One type of parenting style is known as the authoritative parenting style, which is defined by an optimal maintaining a healthy equilibrium between being responsive and demanding; and guiding children in a manner that is reasonable, problem-oriented, and disciplined by elaborating on the rationale behind the rules. It does exceptionally well in each of the four aspects of family functioning. According to Maccoby (1992), authoritative parents are aware of and comprehend the concept of children's autonomy. They also foster verbal communication, permit children to take part in the decision-making process of the family, and desire for children to gradually take on more responsibility for responding to the requirements of other members of the family within their capabilities. The characteristics of this type of parenting style include a constellation of high-standard parental characteristics, such as a high level of emotional attachment and support for children, the encouragement of a two-way communication between parents and children, and the consistent implementation of the rules that have been established by parents (Baumrind, 1991). As stated by Baumrind (1971, 1991), the authoritative parenting style has been found to have a favorable correlation with many developmental outcomes of children. These outcomes include academic success and social behaviors. Furthermore, Holmbeck (1996) observed that the authoritative parenting style is the most advantageous for children and adolescents. This is due to the fact that it is positively associated to a multitude of positive outcomes, such as self-esteem and self-reliance.

The second type of parenting style is known as the authoritarian parenting style, and it is characterized by behaviors that are extremely demanding and excessively restricting. There is a high level of control and maturity standards, but there is a low level of nurturing and communication in both directions between your parents and your children. Authoritarian parents are those who restrict their children's independence and who want their children to obey their stringent parental rules and instructions without question. They do this by threatening severe punishments in the event that their children violate these rules and orders. Children whose parents are authoritarian are more likely to experience feelings of anxiety, social withdrawal, and overall dissatisfaction, as seen by Baumrind (1967, 1971).

(3) The permissive parenting style, also known as the indulgent parenting style, is the opposite of the restrictive parenting style. It is characterized by high levels of responsiveness and a lack of restrictions. It has a high level of nurturing, but it has a low level of maturity needs, supervision, and communication in both directions between parents and children. The permissive parenting style, as described by Baumrind (1989), is characterized by a careless approach in which parents make few demands, encourage their children to express their feelings, and barely use power to gain control over their behavior. Additionally, parents tend to not require mature behavior from their children, but instead encourage their children's independence. The authors Hetherington and Parke (1986) found that children who were raised by parents who were overly indulgent exhibited poor levels of self-reliance, achievement oriented, and self-control. According to Maccabey and Martin (1983), the fourth type of parenting style is the neglecting or uninvolved parenting style. This style of parenting is characterized by a low level of responsiveness and demandingness in both dimensions. It is believed to be the most detrimental of the four types of parenting styles on the development of children and adolescents. Specifically, children who are raised by parents who are neglectful are more likely to exhibit a number of negative developmental outcomes. These consequences include being impulsive, aggressive, non-compliant with rules and commands, moody, and generally having low self-esteem or confidence. Children, as Hetherington and Parke (1986) pointed out, are typically

Research has shown that children and adolescents who come from households with authoritative parents are more capable and efficient in terms of their social and academic lives compared to those whose parents are not authoritative (Baumrind, 1991; Maccoby & Martin, 1983; Baumrind, 1991).

2003; Weiss and Schwarz, 1996; Miller et al., 1993). In general, over the course of the last three decades, a significant amount of research has been conducted to investigate the impact of parenting on the various developmental outcomes of children, adolescents, and young adults. This research has utilized a three or four typological approach, in which the influences of the primary dimensions of parenting behavior are accumulated to form the four distinct parenting styles (namely, authoritative, authoritarian, indulgent, and neglectful parenting styles) or specific dimensions of parenting behavior approach. Parenting is a significant factor in determining whether or not children and adolescents achieve optimal developmental outcomes. These research have produced consistent evidence that parenting plays a major role in this regard. Due to the tremendous impact that it has on students' learning, perseverance, and academic achievement, the notion of motivation has received considerable interest among researchers from a wide variety of psychological and philosophical perspectives in a variety of academic fields, particularly in the fields of psychology and education. Over the course of the last few decades, it

has been put into action and put into reality based on a variety of theoretical approaches. With regard to human motivation, for instance, Maslow (1970) defined it as the urge that motivates individuals to strive for a goal, taking into consideration both internal and external circumstances. In its most fundamental form, this motivation is founded on the hierarchical organization of human wants. Pintrich and Schunk define motivation as the cognitive process that activates and maintains goal-oriented activity (Pintrich & Schunk, 1996, page 4). This definition indicates that motivation can be characterized as the same thing. One way to define motivation is as the psychological process that inspires, guides, and maintains a person's conduct. In general, motivation can be stated as the process. It is a term that refers to both internal and external influences that have an effect on an individual to participate in acts that are goal-oriented and to continue undertaking such actions. In spite of the fact that there are other types of motivation that influence human behavior, psychologists have mostly focused their attention on the motivation of accomplishment because of the distinct impact it has on individuals' decisions on whether or not to participate in particular activities or engage in particular tasks. The American psychologist Henry Murray is credited with being the person who initiated the study of the factors that motivate people to attain their goals. Murray described achievement motivation as the "desire to accomplish something difficult; to master, manipulate... to overcome difficulties and attain a high standard; to excel oneself; to compete and surpass others; to increase self-regard by the successful exercise of talent" (Murray, 1938, p. 164). Murray's definition was published in 1938. McClelland, Atkinson, Clark, and Lowell (1953) did research after studying Murray's books. The primary focus of their investigation was on the individual's drive to achieve achievement, and they created the theoretical foundations upon which this drive is based. They referred to the want for achievement, also known as accomplishment motivation, as "a strong desire to succeed." It is stated by the author that there is a competition to achieve a particular level of excellence (p.110). Achievement motivation is understood as the outcome of an emotional conflict between the desire for success and the anxiety of failure, according to the standard research conducted by McClelland. In the context of achievement scenarios, the authors contend that the outcome of a particular conduct acts as a factor that determines subsequent behavior. In 1953, McClelland and colleagues proposed theoretical frameworks for accomplishment motivation. McClelland himself offered these frameworks in 1961. Several theories of motivation have been developed as a result of these frameworks. Some of these ideas include the achievement goal theory (which was reviewed by Ames and Archer in 1988; Middleton and Midgley in 1997; Pintrich and Schunk in 1996) and the expectancy-value theory (which was reviewed by Eccles et al. in 1983; Wigfield and Eccles in 2000). The purpose of these ideas is to provide an explanation for the impact that achievement motivation has on the behavior of an individual in general, and on their academic success in particular. For the purpose of understanding the influence that motivation has on academic achievement, the self-determination theory (SDT), which was initially presented by Deci and Ryan (1985, 1991), is the theory that is utilized the most frequently. According to Deci and Ryan's contention, self-determination theory (SDT) is a conceptual framework that can be utilized to comprehend human motivation. Competence, relatedness, and autonomy are the three essential psychological demands that are said to be intrinsic to every human, according to the theory of social psychological theory (SDT). In order to achieve the

highest possible level of psychological well-being, it is necessary to satisfy certain demands, which are thought to be universal. Within the scope of this discussion, the word "self-determination" refers to the degree to which individuals are able to exercise control over their conduct without being subject to any external limitations. Specifically, the self-determination theory (SDT) places an emphasis on the significance of the psychological need for autonomy. This theory proposes that individuals have the capacity to exercise their own will and make independent decisions when it comes to starting, directing, maintaining, and controlling their own activities. An attempt that is followed for the purpose of fulfilling one's need for fulfillment and contentment that comes from gaining knowledge, conducting research, or making an effort to comprehend something unfamiliar. The act of participating in a task with the intention of reaching a certain outcome or gaining tangible rewards is an example of extrinsic motivation. This is in contrast to activities that are performed for the purpose of obtaining the intrinsic enjoyment or personal satisfaction that comes from finishing the work. An absence of intention to act, complete inaction, or action without aim are all examples of behavior that can be classified as motivation. Along the self-determination continuum, the researchers hypothesized that as an individual moves from amotivation to intrinsic motivation, the various levels of motivation are connected with increasingly more favorable developmental outcomes for the individual. This was the hypothesis that was put out by the researchers. A three-part classification system for intrinsic motivation has been presented by researchers in the field of psychology (Deci, 1975; Deci & Ryan, 1985, 1991, 2000; Deci, Vallerand, Pelletire, & Ryan 1991; Ryan & Deci, 2000; Vallerand et al., 1992). This system is comprised of three unique categories. This article will discuss the three different types of intrinsic motivation, which are as follows: intrinsic motivation for information, intrinsic motivation for achievement, and intrinsic motivation for stimulation. When we talk about an individual's intrinsic motivation to acquire knowledge, we are referring to the inherent drive that exists within them to engage in a particular activity for the purpose of experiencing pleasure and satisfaction that is derived from the act of carrying out the task, acquiring knowledge, exploring, or attempting to comprehend something novel to do with the task. An individual's inner urge to participate in a work for the goal of enjoying enjoyment and satisfaction received from seeking to accomplish or create something describes what is referred to as the individual's intrinsic motivation to achieve. a desire within oneself to seek out and participate in exciting new events An individual's internal drive to accomplish a task in order to experience enjoyable feelings, such as sensory pleasure, aesthetic experiences, amusement, and enjoyment, is referred to as stimulation. Stimulation is a drive that is internal to the individual. Please see the writings of Deci (1975), Deci & Ryan (1985, 1991, 2000), Ryan & Deci (2000), and. This definition was provided by the authors of the definition. On a continuum of self-determination, psychologists (Deci, 1975; Deci & Ryan, 1985, 1991, 2000; Deci, Vallerand, Pelletire, & Ryan 1991; Ryan & Deci, 2000) have found four different types of extrinsic motivation. These types of motivation are in addition to the intrinsic motivation that researchers have identified. Ascending in terms of self-determination, the following categories are included in this list: Regulation can be broken down into four categories: external regulation, introjected regulation, identified regulation, and integrated regulation. External regulation refers to behaviors that are controlled through external processes, such as incentives and constraints (Deci & Ryan, 1985, 1991, 1995, 2000; Ryan & Deci, 2000).

These behaviors are referred to as "external regulation." Introjected regulation is a term that describes behaviors that are regulated by an individual, yet the individual does not fully acknowledge the regulation as being their own. According to Deci and Ryan (1995), it is a style of regulation that is relatively influenced by the outside world, in which behavioral actions are carried out in order to prevent feelings of guilt or anxiety, or in order to acquire ego enhancements such as pride. The term "identified regulation" refers to the voluntary activities that an individual chooses to engage in because they believe that these actions are vital for their own well-being. This sort of control is self-determined, and Deci and Ryan have conducted substantial research on it, publishing their findings in a number of articles between the years 1985 and 2000. When we talk about integrated regulation, we are referring to regulations that have been completely ingrained into the feeling of who we are as individuals. These regulations have been thoroughly examined, and it has been determined that they are in accordance with the individual's other requirements and values (Deci & Ryan, 1985, 1991; Ryan & Deci, 2000). While these researchers categorized integrated regulation as a form of extrinsic motivation, other investigators (such as Vallerand et al., 1992) discovered that integrated regulation was not perceived as a reason for engaging in educational activities and could not be differentiated from identified regulation. Bandura's (1977, 1982, 1986, 1997) social cognitive theory defines self-efficacy as an individual's belief in their ability to effectively plan and carry out actions necessary to attain specified goals. Self-efficacy helps individuals believe that they are able to achieve their goals. The social cognitive theory of personality developed by Bandura serves as the foundation for the concept of self-efficacy. According to this idea, people are not passive beings who are simply influenced by external stimuli or who are driven by unconscious urges; rather, they are proactive, self-reflective, and self-regulating beings. In addition, it sheds light on the fact that the functioning and acts of a human are the consequence of a dynamic interaction between three essential components. The three components are as follows: (i) the behavior of an individual; (ii) personal elements such as thoughts and beliefs; and (iii) the conditions of the environment. All three of these elements have an influence on one another that is mutually beneficial. This type of relationship between two parties is referred to by Bandura as reciprocal determinism, which he characterizes as having a triadic shape. An additional observation made by Bandura was that self-efficacy can be derived from four different sources. The four types of experiences that contribute to learning are: (i) Mastery experience, which refers to personal experience of successfully completing a task; (ii) Vicarious experience, which involves learning from observing others perform a task; (iii) Verbal persuasion, which entails receiving encouragement and support from others; and (iv) Physiological state, which involves managing one's emotional arousal, including fatigue, stress, and anxiety levels. According to Bandura (1977, 1986), the personal experience of successfully completing a task is the most immediate and powerful source of self-efficacy. This information was gleaned from his research. Usher and Pajares (2008) made the observation that the most influential factor in determining one's level of self-efficacy is typically one's personal history of successful experiences. But the effects of these encounters can vary from person to person, depending on factors such as gender, ethnicity, and academic ability, among other things. There is also the possibility that the sources of self-efficacy beliefs are influenced by the particular academic field that is being evaluated. According to Bandura's theory, self-efficacy is a multifaceted term that influences people's

performance in both direct and indirect ways. It has an effect on a number of factors that determine outcomes, such as self-regulation, mood, attribution, and motivation. (Bandura, 1977, 1994; Pajares, 2002; Schunk, 1991, 1995) Numerous researchers have demonstrated that self-efficacy beliefs have a considerable influence on the selection of tasks, the amount of effort put out, the level of perseverance, the level of resilience, and the level of individual accomplishment. The concept of self-efficacy is restricted to specific activities and tasks that take place inside particular environments and circumstances. The belief is not one that is held by everyone, but rather one that is limited to particular situations. It was Bandura in 1977, 1986, and 1997, and Jackson in 2002. A more straightforward explanation would be that people do not have the same level of self-efficacy. On the other hand, the level of self-efficacy beliefs that an individual possesses is dependent on the particular task that is being performed as well as the setting in which it is being carried out. The extensive research on self-efficacy has been carried out in a variety of specific fields, such as the academic world, social interactions, professional growth, clinical settings, athletics, and health (Bandura, 1997). Because of this, the specific kind of self-efficacy that is applicable in an academic setting is referred to as academic self-efficacy. Self-evaluation is a term that describes the process by which an individual evaluates their own capabilities and the possibility of obtaining success in academic contexts. Specifically, this particular facet of self-efficacy is the focus of the current research that is being conducted. Students who have high levels of academic self-efficacy beliefs are more likely to exhibit positive feelings, attitudes, and ideas, according to a number of research. They are able to motivate themselves and take the required activities, they are able to persevere in the face of hurdles until they find a solution, they consider failure as a brief setback that they can overcome, and they apply a variety of tactics to deal with issues and stay on track. These students do not allow themselves to be frightened by challenging projects and tasks; rather, they view them as chances for learning and progressing toward expertise. Bandura (1977, 1994); Pajares (2002); Schunk (1991, 1995) are some of the authors. As a result, these characteristics add to the success they have achieved in studies. In contrast, students who have poor self-efficacy beliefs may not be interested in completing assignments, may experience feelings of being threatened by difficult situations, and may intentionally avoid those situations. They may also exhibit a lower level of dedication to the accomplishment of goals and make an effort to avoid activities that require cognitive processing. Furthermore, these students have a tendency to conclude that their failures might be attributed to a lack of ability to persevere in the face of adversity (Bandura, 1977, 1994; Pajares, 2002; Schunk, 1991, 1995). Self-efficacy beliefs have been shown to have an effect on a variety of factors, including task selection, goal orientation, exertion, resolve, flexibility, and accomplishment, as demonstrated by these research. The connection between the parenting style and the academic performance of children:

An investigation was conducted by Gupta and Mehtani (2017) to investigate the correlation between the parenting styles that students self-reported and their academic performance in school. The level of academic accomplishment was the dependent variable in this study. The independent variables were parenting styles (autocratic, democratic, permissive, and uninvolved), as well as demographic factors such as the type of school attended (public versus private) and gender (male versus female). The findings of the study were significant in that they

brought to light the primary influences that parenting style and gender have on the academic success of students. However, there was no noticeable impact brought about by the type of school. According to the findings of the study, there was no discernable link found between the academic accomplishment of senior secondary school students and the parenting style, school type, or gender of the students. According to the findings of the study, the interplay between parenting style and gender had a substantial impact on the academic performance of high school students. In their study from 2017, Jaiswal and Choudhuri investigated the association between parenting practices, such as parenting style, parental expectations, and parental engagement at home, and the academic accomplishment of elementary and middle school pupils. Specifically, they looked at the data that was accessible to them. It has been established through empirical research that different types of parental participation have a major influence in a number of different elements. The evidence reveals that there is a direct connection between a parenting style that is authoritative and academic achievement at all levels of education. Having said that, this correlation may be different for different people based on their racial origin, cultural background, and personal financial situation. The purpose of the comprehensive study that Pinquart, M. (2016) conducted on 308 empirical studies was to determine whether or not there is a correlation between various parenting traits, such as parenting style, and the grade point average or academic performance of children or teenagers. It was established that the significance of parental sensitivity was determined by performing research that was both simultaneous and comprehensive. While the statistical significance of these benefits was not significant, there was a correlation between improved academic accomplishment and success in warmth, behavioral control, independence grant, or authoritative parenting. This was the case even if the statistical significance of these benefits was not significant. Studies have shown that children who are subjected to high levels of psychological control or supervision from their parents are less likely to achieve success in their lives. The ability to predict changes in academic accomplishment over a certain time frame was demonstrated by a variety of factors and parenting approaches, with the exception of three variables. A number of factors, including the quality of the parents, the success metric, the publication status, the race of the child, and the reporter, all played a moderating role in the relationship between academic achievement and the degree to which they influenced the children.

Objectives of the study

- To examine the correlation between Academic Motivation, Anxiety, and Academic Performance in adolescents.
- To examine the correlation between anxiety levels and academic achievement in adolescents

Hypotheses

- There would be positive correlation among Academic Motivation, Anxiety, and Academic Performance in adolescents.
- There would be negative correlation between anxiety levels and academic achievement in adolescents.

Methods

The Academic Motivation Inventory (AMI - MKS) is a tool used to measure a person's motivation in an academic setting. Misra, K. S. (2020)

The Academic Motivation Inventory (AMI - lvfK.S) was developed by Misra, K.S. in 2020. This inventory comprises a total of 46 items. Participants have the option to provide their response on a five-point rating scale, which includes the categories of strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, and strongly disagree. There are two distinct categories of items: positive and negative. Participants have the option to provide their responses using a five-point rating system, consisting of the categories 'strongly agree', 'agree', 'undecided', 'disagree', and 'strongly disagree'. In order to assess the positive item scale, allocate a score of 5 to 'strongly agree', 4 to 'agree', 3 to 'undecided', 2 to 'disagree', and 1 to 'strongly disagree'. To assign scores to the negative item scale, give a score of 1 to 'strongly agree', 2 to 'agree', 3 to 'undecided', 4 to 'disagree', and 5 to 'strongly disagree'. It was given to pupils in grades nine to eleven. The split-half reliability coefficient for AMI has been shown to be 0.875. The alpha value is 0.871. Expert opinion has been used to establish the face validity.

The Sinha Anxiety Scale, developed by Sinha in 1969, is a tool used to measure levels of anxiety.

The researcher personally gathered the final data for the present study in order to maintain a consistent testing situation and assure the acquisition of valid and accurate data under the current circumstances. The researcher reached out to the principals of the chosen schools and obtained consent to collect data. Once the researcher had arranged suitable seating arrangements, they proceeded to create a strong rapport with the pupils. Subsequently, test booklets were disseminated and a concise explanation of the testing objective was provided. Assurances were provided regarding the maintenance of stringent confidentiality for the information. Students were instructed to actively and genuinely participate in the study, since it was anticipated to uncover significant features related to their conduct and academic performance.

The Parenting Style Scale (PSS GMMD) developed by Gupta and Mehtani (2017).

Scale for assessing parenting styles PSS Grvi:MD was authored by Gupta and Mehtan in 2017. This scale comprises 44 items that are categorized into four distinct parenting styles: Democratic, Autocratic, Permissive, and Uninvolved. The administration was carried out among 600 students, including those in secondary school, senior secondary school, and college. Each item on the scale has five possibilities. The five selections correspond to five responses: 'often', 'often', 'occasionally', 'rarely', and 'never'. Assign a score of 4 to the scale.

Assign a score of 3 to "always," a score of 3 to "often," a score of 2 to "sometimes," a score of 1 to "rarely," and a score of 0 to "never" responses. The reliability of the scale was established using the test-retest method and split-half approach, by administering the parenting style scale to a representative sample. The test-retest reliability coefficient was calculated to be 0.91, which indicates a high level of consistency.

Result and Discussion

This section presents the results of the quantitative analysis. The data analysis involved scoring all participant replies according to the normal scoring techniques specified in the relevant scale manuals. The scores were subsequently inputted into SPSS version. The final analyses were performed after calculating the totals for each dimension of the scales in SPSS.

The results of these research are presented in the following three sections. The correlation coefficient values, which were produced to demonstrate the relationship between the study's predictor and Variables that are tied to a specific criterion. Following the discovery of a substantial correlation, the subsequent This section summarizes the results of the stepwise multiple regression analysis conducted to investigate. Assess the extent to which the predictor variables accurately predicted the criterion variable. The final findings of the 2 x 2 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were obtained to determine significant differences between the independent and dependent variables.

A Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was computed. SPSS will be used to evaluate the correlation between parenting style and academic motivation, as well as their impact on anxiety and academic success. The descriptive statistics and correlation coefficient for these variables are displayed below the tables.

Table-I presents the descriptive data for the dimensions of Parenting style, Academic Motivation, Anxiety, and Academic Performance among Adolescents.

Table-I: *Descriptive statistics of dimensions of Parenting style ,Academic Motivation , Anxiety and Academic performance among Adolescents*

Table 1.1 Summary of correlations of dimensions of Parenting Style with Academic Motivation, Anxiety and Academic Performance among adolescents

Variables	Democratic Parenting style	Autocratic Parenting style	Permissive Parenting style	Uninvolved Parenting style
Academic Motivation	0.591 **	-0.72**	-0.606**	-0.644**
Anxiety	-0.453* *	0.491 **	0.441**	0.471 **
Academic performance	0.466**	-0.506**	-0.432**	-0.397**

** statistically significant at the 0.01 level

The associations between the various aspects of Parenting Styles and Academic Motivation:

The table above displays the outcomes of a Pearson product moment correlation study, which was undertaken to examine the level of connection between parenting style factors and academic motivation. The findings indicated a favorable and significant association ($r = 0.591$, $p < 0.01$) between academic motivation and the democratic parenting style of teenagers. The connection between academic motivation and the autocratic parenting style of teenagers was -0.72 , which was statistically significant at the 0.01 level. This value also demonstrated the inverse correlation between them. A strong negative association was observed between the academic motivation and the permissive parenting style of teenagers ($r = -0.606$, $p < 0.01$). The association between academic motivation and uninvolved parenting style of teenagers was found to be -0.644 , which is statistically significant at the 0.01 level ($r = -0.644$, $p < 0.01$). The data also demonstrated a negative correlation between the two variables, which was clearly obvious in Table I. Specifically, the uninvolved parenting style had a stronger negative link with academic motivation compared to the permissive parenting style. The overall findings suggest that autocratic, permissive, and uninvolved parenting styles were found to have a negative correlation with academic motivation, with the exception of the democratic parenting style.

The associations between various aspects of Parenting Styles and Anxiety: The findings from Table I.I indicate a substantial negative correlation (-0.453) between the democratic parenting style and anxiety levels in teenagers. This correlation was statistically significant at the 0.01 level ($r = -0.453$, $p < .01$). Additionally, the results demonstrate a negative link between these two variables. The connection between the autocratic parenting style and anxiety in adolescents was found to be 0.491 , which is statistically significant at a p-value of less than 0.01 ($r = 0.491$, $p < .01$). This value likewise demonstrated the favorable correlation between them. The association between the permissive parenting style and anxiety in adolescents was 0.441 , indicating a substantial relationship. a level with a correlation coefficient of 0.441 , which is statistically significant at a p-value of less than 0.01. The findings also indicated a favorable link between them. The connection between the lack of involvement in parenting style and anxiety in adolescents was 0.471 , which was statistically significant at the 0.01 level ($r = 0.471$, $p < .01$). Furthermore, it demonstrated a clear and favorable correlation between them.

The associations between several aspects of Parenting Styles and Academic Performance: The findings from table I.I indicated a significant correlation ($r = 0.466$, $p < .01$) between the democratic parenting style and academic achievement of all adolescents. These results also demonstrated a favorable association between the two variables. The study found a substantial negative association ($r = -0.506$, $p < .01$) between the authoritarian parenting style and the academic achievement of teenagers. This value also demonstrated the inverse correlation between them. The correlation

coefficient between the permissive parenting style and academic achievement of teenagers was -0.432, which was statistically significant at the 0.01 level ($r = -0.432, p < 0.01$). Additionally, the findings indicated a negative link between them. The association between the uninvolved parenting style and academic achievement of teenagers was -0.397, which was statistically significant at the 0.01 level ($r = -0.397, p < .01$). It also demonstrated the inverse correlation between them.

The overall data indicated a strong and positive correlation between the authoritarian parenting style and anxiety among teenagers, in comparison to permissive and uninvolved parenting styles. The study found a strong and favorable correlation between the democratic parenting style and academic performance among teenagers.

Table 1.2 presents a concise overview of the relationships between academic motivation, anxiety, and academic performance in teenagers.

		performance
Academic Motivation	-0.677**	0.598**

** significant at .01 level

The relationship between academic motivation and anxiety, as well as its impact on academic performance: The results (table 1.2) indicated a link between academic motivation and anxiety. The correlation coefficient of -0.677 is statistically significant at the 0.01 level ($r = -0.677, p < .01$), indicating a negative association between the variables.

The findings from table 1.2 indicate a substantial association ($r=0.598, p<0.01$) between academic motivation and academic achievement across all adolescents. The findings also demonstrated a favorable link between them. In summary, the results of this study indicate that teenagers who displayed high levels of motivation exhibited lower levels of anxiety and higher levels of academic performance.

Table 1.3 presents a concise overview of the link between anxiety and academic achievement among adolescents.

The findings from table 1.3 indicated a substantial negative correlation (-0.441) between anxiety and academic performance among adolescents. This connection was statistically significant at the 0.01 level ($r = -0.441, p<0.01$). Furthermore, it demonstrated the inverse correlation between them. These data indicate a strong correlation between high levels of anxiety and poor academic performance.

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Online Resources:

The American Psychological Association (APA) and the National Association of School Psychologists (NASP) websites often have relevant articles and resources on parenting styles and their impact on child development and academic outcomes.